

"MOVEMENT AND TONE" METHOD IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7855181>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th April 2023

Accepted: 21th April 2023

Online: 22th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Children's activity, making a tone with the help of clapping, modern and non-traditional pedagogical technology, creating music with the help of clapping, moments of rest.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the author introduces students to the science of physical education offer to use a new interactive method created by him in order to form his attitude does. In this case, the introduction of the lesson is a general development of the students using the melody perform the exercises by moving, that is, by dividing the body parts into four parts (neck, arms, waist, legs) separate exercises for each section and clapping with the help of hands implies that they perform exercises.

Today, the young generation who will raise the status of our country to higher levels in the future, boys and girls who strengthen the borders of our country and are strong, educated and intelligent in every way in addition to growing up, for them to be physically strong, especially sports and great attention is paid to physical education. This is the achievements in the field of sports the laws and decisions adopted in this regard, various sports events organized in our country, exhibitions, especially the delivery of sports equipment to remote village schools It is healthy to carry out a number of important reforms in our country and an important factor in realizing the noble goal of raising a mature generation is happening. Therefore, now he completes physical education lessons in schools on his own there is a need to start. In this place, it is very important to conduct physical education classes at a high level in rural schools important. Because rural students are more interested in physical education classes in city schools students are no less interested. Now only from these possibilities effective use and interest of students in physical education classes, physical education depends on the level of skills, knowledge and skills of the teacher. For this purpose, systematic organization of education and training based on comprehensive and clear plans should be done. Advanced pedagogical technology methods in teaching physical education with students - When using methods such as "Brainstorming", "Working in a small group", "Zig-zag", "Game" it became clear from pedagogical experiences that the effectiveness of teaching is much higher. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies during the lesson increases the quality of education is of great practical importance. Use of interactive methods in physical education classes requires great skill. As we know, children's activities mainly consist of play, and their desires are fulfilled physical education classes will come in handy. Because the child plays

during the lesson, jumps, runs, in short, feels free. That is why they are in school they look forward to every physical education subject they pass. Taking into account these interests of children, physical education classes are further developed you can pass in an interesting, festive way and use music for this. Here is my non-traditional work that I have created and continue to support in my work I recommend my method. This technique is called Motion and Tone. This method also unconventional and interesting for children, where and in what conditions of the lesson (whether no excessive movement (anxiety) regardless of whether it is done outside, in the hall or in the classroom not required. Music can be played easily by hand. That is, each In the introductory part of the lesson, a set of general developmental exercises is given. These are the exercises actions can be performed by creating a sound - melody. In this case, the body parts are four divided into sections (neck, arms, back and legs), separate exercises for each section is given and clapped with hands. Exercises for each body part in between, the action called "Naqorat" is repeated. So this method is action It is interpreted as implementation with the help of melody (clapping). Now I recommend this set of exercises: 1. Initial position: standing position, hands feet in front of the chest, 1. tilting the head to the right and clapping "lay" is released, 2- to the left, 3- to the front, 4- to the back and clap in the same tone the action is continued. Recitation: Initial position: standing position, legs in a pair position, with the body to the left (right) side turning and bending the knees, five claps are played and the melody of "lalay-lay" is released.

2. Initial position: standing position, legs in a double position, 1- hands extended forward and one clap

2- raise the hands up and clap in this way,

3- hands are lowered to the side, 4- initial position.

3. Initial position: standing position, feet shoulder-width apart, arms raised on four

forwards four times and four times backward, hands are highest and lowest after connecting at the point, a "lay" tone is released by clapping one hand. Recitation: Initial position: standing position, legs in a pair position, with the body to the left (right) side turning and bending the knees, five claps are played and the melody of "lalay-lay" is released.

4. Initial position: standing position, feet shoulder width apart, 1- bent to the left, hands on the chest one clapping in front makes a "lay" sound, 2- the same action on the right side performed, 3- when bending to the front, hands are clapped down, 4- to the back the same tone is made by clapping hands in front of the chest.

5. Initial position: standing position, feet shoulder width apart, without bending the knees 1- forward bending down and clapping one clap at the lowest point, the tone "lay" is formed, raising the 2nd body the same position is repeated with the hands raised high. Refrain. Initial position: standing position, legs in a pair, with the body to the left (right). turning and bending the knees, five claps are played and the melody of "lalay-lay" is released.

6. Initial position: standing position, in the 1st sitting position, hands are extended forward and one clap The tone of "lay" is formed, 2- standing up and clapping one hand above, the tone of "lay" is formed will be done.

7. Initial position: standing position, right (left) leg in front, left (right) leg behind, feet We jump and clap our hands to the tune of "Lay-Lay" while changing our positions. As we know, depending on the age of students, the number of exercises changes - increases. This and

the possibility to change the number of exercises given for each part of the body we have Adjust the tone for new exercises as the number of exercises changes it is necessary to try to find out that this situation is not as difficult as it seems. Girls in the calculation of division in physical education lessons from the "Movement and tone" method groups, in pre-school educational institutions based on the requirements of DTS, secondary morning physical education in the primary classes of the school program, in higher educational institutions can also be used in exercises and production enterprises. At the same time, the humanities and social sciences in the school program are being taught fatigue of the brain in students, fatigue and boredom falling on the body or in minutes of physical training used to prevent symptoms such as fatigue can also be used.

Through this method, which I used in my work, the interest of young people in sports, I tried to increase his love. It is not surprising that even the youth of our village is the world today They grew up in the village where they are conquering the arenas and became the proud children of our nation If famous athletes such as Muhammadkadir Abdullayev and Rishod Sobirov develop. They say that movement is the treasure of life. Because life does not open its great treasure by itself. It can be opened by constant action, independent work, and striving. Everyone in life should be in motion regularly. Otherwise, from progress in today's fast-paced world can be left behind. That's why you should always be on the move, on your own to work, not to be afraid of life's difficulties, to overcome difficulties only through hard work and effort it is necessary to overcome. Physical activity cleanses a person's soul, strengthens his strength, spiritual maturity, good thoughts, encouraging a person to do good deeds encourages to conduct. In order to inculcate such concepts in the minds of young people, "Movement and I organized the lessons in an unconventional way using the "tone" method. I think so beautiful ideas, goals in the hearts of the young generation through interesting activities and interesting games quickly penetrates and every student can achieve the goal he has set for himself in his lesson.

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